

Examining destination image and Muslim tourists' behavioral intention using the theory of planned behavior

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ABSTRACT

Destination image has been empirically proven to have a significant influence on the behavioral intention of tourists, while limited studies have been done to explore the relationship between destination image and behavioral intention of a Muslim tourist when visiting a destination. Empirical studies highlight the importance of a positive destination image on the behavioral intention of a Muslim tourist. The primary purpose of this study is to explain the relationship between destination image and behavioral intention with the aid of the theory of planned behavior in the context of Asia and empirical evidence is extracted from various studies conducted in Asian countries. Attracting more Muslim tourists has been a challenge for various countries and while so, the concept of halal tourism has been recently recognized in academia, is in need of research to study the gaps and challenges faced when increasing the number of Muslim tourists in the world. This study highlights the link between destination image and intention to travel of tourists and hence this paper provides a theoretical overview of the Theory of planned behavior and its application to the destination image and behavioral intention of Muslim tourists. Data was gathered from numerous literature compiled by various researchers. Empirical studies conducted in various Asian countries provide evidence that destination image plays a vital role in either creating a positive image or a negative image of the destination and this highly influences the intention of the Muslim tourist to travel to the destination or not. Studies confirm that having Muslim-friendly services attract more Muslim tourists to the destination.

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INTRODUCTION

Tourism is becoming one of the most progressing industry in the global economy and play an important part in the development of the economy contributing to the GDP (Global Domestic Product) and with the development of the tourism industry all over the world, Muslim tourists are also becoming the global tourists (Crescentrating, 2020). Furthermore, Muslim tourists are becoming a large segment in the global tourism industry due to various reasons including, increase of disposable income among Muslim families as well as transition of single-income families to dual-income families (Crescentrating, 2020). According to Pew Research Centre in 2014, growth of the Muslim population is rapid and is expected to reach 26% of the world's population by 2030 and due to the social media advertising destinations as Muslim-friendly (Abdullah and Mustafa, 2018). Thomson Reuters and Dinar standard, estimated value of Muslim tourists currently represents 10% of the travel market and spending was US\$ 126 billion in 2011 and is estimated to reach US\$ 192 billion by 2020 (Abdullah and Mustafa, 2018). Authors such as Duman, highlighted the importance of the world "familiarizing to Muslim tourist satisfaction" due to the increase in Muslim tourists and the fact that Muslims are deemed to travel to the destinations which is more Muslim-friendly (Abdullah & Mustafa, 2018).

Muslim Friendly Tourism (MFT) is where destinations learn the Islamic attributes most important to the Muslim and incorporating or designing the services and products of the destination in a way that Muslims are able to be satisfied without having to compromise their Islamic faith and in addition, these researchers suggest that Muslims regard their Islamic faith very important and is drawn towards destinations which employ Islamic values and provide services according to the Islamic faith (Al-Gasawneh & Al-Adamat, 2020). According to Haque and Chowdhury (2019), destination image play a vital role in the perception of the Muslim tourist and how this perception eventually lead to the behavioral intention and finally committing the behavior to travel to the destination and this claim is empirically proven by Crescentrating's Global Muslim Travel index which is measured annually from Muslim travelers on their vote as the destinations they prefer travelling more and the reason for choosing these destinations, which resulted that Muslims are more drawn towards destinations which has Muslim-friendly services. The purpose of this study is to analyze various previous empirical studies conducted on destination image and Muslim tourist behavioral intention in the context of Asia. In addition, compendium of literature is examined on how previous studies link destination image and its influence on the Muslim behavioral intention.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Destination Image

Explained by Alcocer & Ruiz (2020), destination image is the cognitive perception of a tourist on a destination and destination image is a very important element in the marketing strategies of destinations as the distinctive destination image of each destination makes it unique and gives competitive advantage over other destinations. There has been extensive research on destination image due to its importance in the success of tourism which identifies how destination image can have an impact on the behavioral intention of the tourist to visit the destination or revisit the destination (Alcocer & Ruiz, 2020). According to Rashid, Wangbenmad & Mansor (2020) highlighted that Muslim-friendly attributes in the destination play a vital role in turning the destination image towards a very positive image in the minds of the Muslim tourist. Yagmur & Aksu (2020) argued that destination image influences the behavioral intention of Muslim tourists while research has given evidence that positive destination image influence the behavioral intention to visit and revisit the destination while negative destination image has shown to drive the Muslim tourist away from the destination. Similarly, Irfan, Mahfudnurnajamuddin, Hasan & Mapparenta (2020) highlighted that destination image has significant effect on behavioral intention of the tourist as study has shown that with positive destination image, the tourist is highly likely to visit the destination again and again. According to Khairunnisah, Sulhaini & Mulyono (2020), previous research has shown that appealing attributes within a destination improves the destination image which has an influence on the behavioural intention of Mulsim tourits. Alexander, Iddrisu & Kojo (2020) revealed that studies have shown that percieved values on the destination has shown strong relationship between tourist satisfaction and loyalty while positive

perceived value on the destination highly influences behavioural intention. Ulfy, Haque, Karim, Hossin, & Huda (2021) argued that positive destination image is empirically seen to have a significant positive influence on the behavioural intention and satisfaction of Muslim tourists.

Explained by Alcocer & Ruiz (2020), one of the most initial research done on destination image by Gunn explained that destination image is highly influence the behavior of a tourist and that destination image has two dimensions; namely organic image and induced image, while the organic image is recognized as that arising from non-commercial or uncontrolled information sources, such as the opinions of friends, magazines, newspapers, news and reports and the induced image is the image that is produced as the end product of various marketing techniques employed by marketers and commercial agents in an attempt to make the public aware of the destination and to promote the destination, in hope of attracting tourists. Destination image was studied by more researchers explaining that cognitive destination image refers to individual's own knowledge and beliefs about the destination (an evaluation of the perceived attributes of the destination) which is a result of an individual's image formed due to the type of marketing techniques the individual was exposed while learning about the destination and affective destination image is explained as a person's individual feeling or the emotional response to a destination (Yagmur & Aksu, 2020). Huete-Alcocer, Martinez-Ruiz, Lopez-Ruiz & Izquiedo-Yusta (2019) explained that conative image is the action done driven by both cognitive image and affective image while destination image as a whole has an effect on the behavioral intention of tourists. Previous researchers included the affective (or psychological) component while other authors has explained that while cognitive image plays a crucial role in convincing the tourist towards the destination, affective image also play a vital role in pursuing the tourist as feelings made up by the tourist has effect on the behavioral intention of the tourist and is demonstrated when a tourist has a negative perception about the destination, even with marketing good convincing marketing techniques, the behavioral intention of the tourist might not be altered or geared towards positive destination image (Huete-Alcocer et al., 2019).

Giving support, some researchers explained that advertisements featuring emotional content such as words associated with positive perception; relaxation, pleasant and exciting convey a destination's affective image (Rashid et al., 2020). On the contrary, Ragab, Mahrous & Ghoneim (2019) argued that most prominent segment of these is the cognitive image and affective image as they portray the perception of the tourist about the destination and the framework used by Gartner used not only the cognitive and affective components but also the conative components is only able to provide a more subtle explanation of the relationships between the main elements of destination Furthermore the cognitive component portray the tourist's knowledge, recognition, beliefs, thoughts and awareness of each attribute of a tourism destination while they also recognized various elements that can be used to measure and study destination image and grouped the perceived tourist destination image to measure the cognitive component of image under nine dimensions, namely; natural resources; general infrastructure, tourism infrastructure, tourism leisure and recreation; culture, history, art, political and economic factors, natural environment; social environment and the atmosphere of the place and within each dimension, classified 24 attribute items (Ragab et al., 2019).

Behavioral Intention of Muslim Tourists

Haque, Azam and Chowdhury (2020) behavioral intention as defined, is explained as the intentions to recommend and revisit a destination by a tourist while intention to recommend is the intention to share the experience through communications and intention to revisit is the intention to return to the destination which are likely to be influenced by destination image. Hidayat, Yasin & Jufri (2021) argued that Muslim-friendly attributes has a positive effect on the decision to stay by the Muslim tourists. Research previously conducted and compiled literature on behavioral intention of tourists explored the relationship between destination image and behavioral intentions which give evidence that destination image and behavioral intention is directly related as destination image is a very important factor in influencing the tourist's behavior towards traveling to the destination for the first time (Haque et al., 2020). Islam (2020) stated that negative perceptions on the destination can highly affect the behavioral intention of tourists. Hanafiah & Hamdan (2020) highlighted that islamic attributes in the destination such as availability of Halal food influences a Muslim tourist behavioural intention. Papastathopoulos, Kaminakis &

Mertzanis (2020) explained that various empirical evidence suggest that Islamic attributes in a destination highly influence the behavioural intention of Muslim tourists. Saifudin & Puspita (2020) argued that Millennial Muslim's behavioural intention in travelling is directly related to the availability of Islamic attributes in that destination. Jalasi & Ambad (2020) highlighted that previous research has shown proof that Islamic attributes in a destination influences the behavioural intention of the Muslim tourists. Ramadhani, Kurniawati & Nata (2020) explained that previous researches have proved the fact that destination image and behavioural intention to visit Halal tourism destination is significantly related.

A theory which describes the relationship between destination image and tourist behavioral intention is the theory of place attachment which was initially introduced in environmental psychology in 1980 and has been used in social sciences as well to understand the tourist behavior (Zuraini & Abdullah, 2019). This theory states that tourists develop a prominent emotion to a destination based on the experience they have gathered or based on the experience they have been exposed in relation to the destination and other studies conducted to learn this theory in depth revealed that there are two dimensions of this theory which is place identity and place dependence while, place identity refers to the emotional connection to a place that gives meaning and purpose to life and place dependence, a type of functional dependence, reflects to what extent a destination enables the achievement of desired activities (Zuraini & Abdullah, 2019). Various research has identified that destination behavioral intention can be studied to learn more about related certain tourist behaviors such as destination choice, evaluation and revisit intention and that when a tourist perceives a destination to be pleasant, tourist is more likely to positively evaluate the destination, creating a positive destination image which promotes future intentions to revisit the destination or even recommend the destination to other close relatives, family members and friends (Haque et al., 2020).

Henderson; who conducted several studies on the Muslim tourist behavior states that Muslim consumer market depend on the Islamic belief system and are bended towards the guidelines of Islam including what is permissible to a Muslim (Halal) and what is prohibited to a Muslim (Haram), since due to their faith, at all times and daily activities of a Muslim are dependent on these values, hence, while travelling as well, Muslim's behavior is greatly influenced by these values and the destinations that adhere to the values of Islam (Haque & Chowdhury, 2019). In order for a destination to satisfy a Muslim tourist or to attract a Muslim tourist towards a destination, it is very crucial that the destination be marketed as a Muslim-friendly destination that provide services in compliance with the Islamic values and the hotels give attention to the principles of Islam (Haque & Chowdhury, 2019). More support is given to these studies by leading authority of halal travel; Crescentrating in the years 2010- 2020 and according to the faith-based needs model (2018) of Crescentrating, destinations which provide prayer facilities, water-friendly washrooms, no islamophobia and Ramadhan services pose as the most attractive to the Muslim traveler which was portrayed in the annual Global Muslim Travelling Index (GMTI) voted by Muslims, the destinations as they are more attracted towards travelling (Haque and Chowdhury, 2019). According to Albattat, Pitra, Nishalini, & Azmi (2018), conducted a study which show evidence that Muslim customers had a positive influence on Shariah compliant hotel. Similarly, Ismail, Albattat & Azam (2020) as well as Jumli, Albattat & Yusof (2018), state that Islamic attributes has significant relationship with Muslim tourist satisfaction.

As per the GMTI index Muslim's behavioral intention is drawn towards countries such as Malaysia and Singapore the most due to the availability of the Muslim-friendly services in these countries (Haque & Chowdhury, 2019). Haque and Chowdhury (2019) argued that while destination image greatly influence the behavioral intention of Muslim tourist, destinations which is only marketed for the non-Muslim segment fail to gear the Muslim tourist's attention towards these destination and further clarification provided by these studies revealed that 70% of the Muslim tourists follow global halal standard and to drive or create a positive destination image in the mindset of the tourist, complying to the Islamic values is crucial in attracting and convincing the behavioral intention of Muslim tourists towards a destination. According to Yuliviona, Alias, Abdullah & Azliyanti (2019) various research conducted to learn the behavior of Muslim tourists and the influence destination image has on the behavioral intention revealed that halal tourism has created a dominant effect in the global tourism industry with many countries adopting the Muslim-friendly services in the destination as an attempt to attract more Muslim tourists as, according to these studies, destinations which as Muslim-friendly services create a positive perception among the Muslim tourists which increase the flow of Muslim tourists while it also is being recommended to the

relatives, family and friends by the Muslim tourists. However, it is noted by other researchers that for the hotels and resorts located in the rural areas, adopting Muslim-friendly services pose as a challenge (Yuliviona et al., 2019).

Theory of Planned Behaviour

Theory of planned behavior was first proposed by Icek Ajzen (1985) in his article “from intentions to actions: a theory of planned behavior” while it has been developed from theory of reasoned action by Martin Fishbein in 1980 and has been used in social sciences to predict and explain behaviors pertaining to different aspects of social sciences including social sciences and theory of planned behavior has attitude, subject norm, perceived behavioral control which leads to intention and eventually to behavior (Hasan, Abdullah and Lew, 2019). Study conducted by Hasan et. al, (2019) to explain the behavioral intention of tourists in Bangladesh, it was found out that when the tourists have recognized a behavior as positive (attitude) and if their significant others want them to perform the behavior (subjective norm), this leads to the intention to do the behavior and finally behavior is performed. On the contrary, if the tourist recognizes a suggested behavior as negative and their significant others do not want them to perform the behavior, less likelihood that a behavioral intention be created to perform the behavior (Hasan et al., 2019). Ulker-Demirel & Ciftci (2020) explained that consumer behavior including behavioural intention to visit and revisit destinations has been explained suing theory of planned behavior in several empirical studies. Similarly, Manosuthi, Lee & Han (2020), argued the application of theory of planned behavior in the prediction of behavioral inetntion of tourists in variours empirical research. Yarimoglu & Gunay (2019) highlighted that when theory of planned behavior was used to predict the intention fo Turkish tourists intention to visit green hotels, study showed that relationship between intention to visit green hotels was found to be significiant with the type of enviornemntal-friendly activities being conducted.

Purwanto and Rofiah (2020) conducted a study using theory of planned behavior to dtermine the effect of electronic word-of-mouth on Halal travel interest which shows a significnat relationhship between electronic word-of-mouth and Halal travel interest. Hasan, Biswas, Roy, Akter & Kuri (2020) also conducted a study to examine the relationship among attitude, subjective norms and behavioral inetntion using theory of planned behaviour which portray significnat relationhship between these variables. Wang, Jin, Fan, Ju & Xiao (2020) conducted a study to analyze the preferences of Chinese tourists using theory of planned behavior during travel intention during COVID-19 and was found that areas with strict measures to control COVID-19 has been seen to be preffered by the tourists. Researchers explained Theory of planned behavior or TPB as theory which explain the degree to which a person has a positive or a negative evaluation towards a certain behavior while subjective norms refer to the perceived social pressure to perform or not to perform the behavior while the perceived behavior control is perceived ease or difficulty of performing the behavior and the result of these three elements will lead in the intention and finally to do the (Meng & Cui, 2020). More studies done to learn TPB recognized TPB having two aspects; volitional aspects, such as attitude (behavioral beliefs) and subjective norms (subjective normative beliefs) and non-volitional aspects, such as perceived behavioral control while making the decision by a person to do or perform a certain behavior and further elaborated explained that since there are many factors that come into play when a person directs to a certain behavior, non-volatile elements in this theory is seen to persuade more towards a certain behavior (Meng & Cui, 2020).

Figure 1: Theory of Planned Behavior

OBJECTIVES

The general objective of the study is analyzing the empirical evidence of destination image and behavioral intention of Muslim tourist when visiting the Asian region and the specific objectives are:

1. To study the relationship of destination image and behavioral intention of Muslim tourists.
2. To analyze the relationship of Islamic attributes and destination image.
3. To explore the relationship between Islamic attributes, positive destination image and behavioral intention of Muslim tourists.

METHODS

This study is purely theoretical which used secondary sources from various previous literatures to put together the findings of this study.

Table 1: Seocndary scources

Data gathered	Author/s & year	Region
Muslim travel market statistics	Crescentrating (2020)	All over the globe
Muslim travel market statistics	Abdullah and Mustafa (2018)	All over the globe
Islamic faith and Muslim travel behavior	Al-Gasawneh and Al-Adamat, (2020)	Middle East and Asia
Destination image and tourist loyalty	Haque and Chowdhury (2019)	All over the globe
Destination image, revisit intention	Widjaja et al., (2020)	All over the globe
Destination image, revisit intention	Siregar et al., (2019)	All over the globe
Destination image	Alcocer & Ruiz (2020),	All over the globe
Muslim friendly serivces	Wangbenmad & Mansor (2020)	All over the globe
Destination image and behavioral intention	Yagmur & Aksu (2020)	All over the globe
Destination image and behavioral intention	Ulfy et al. (2021)	All over the globe
Behavioral intention of Muslim tourists	Hidayat et al. (2021)	All over the globe
Behavioral intention of Muslim tourists	Saifudin & Puspita (2020)	All over the globe
Theory of planned behavior	Hasan et al. (2019)	All over the globe
Theory of planned behavior	Meng & Cui, (2020)	Asia

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

While many studies have been done to find out the relationship between destination image and behavioral intention to travel to the destination has been explained using theory of planned behavior, one such empirical study from conducted in Taiwan from 161 Muslim tourists, to find the relationship between destination image and Muslim tourist travel intention, revealed that Muslim tourism positively effect and has a significant effect between destination image and travel intention of the Muslim tourist, while the study also resulted that tourist attitude also has a significant affect between destination image and travel intention (Liu, Li, Yen & Sher, 2018). Another study carried out in Malaysia to examine the effects of various elements on Muslim consumer's purchase behavior with theory of planned behavior revealed that attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control positively affect Muslim consumer purchase intention towards Sharia-Complaint hotels (Haque et al., 2020). Similar study of 302 tourists, conducted to examine and elaborate the theory of planned behavior to tourism by examining tourist intention to revisit Egypt revealed that the extended theory of planned behavior with added constructs; travel motivation, eWOM, destination image and destination familiarity showed a positive relationship between the added constructs and travel intention while role of attitude acts as a mediating role in attitude, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control (Soliman, 2019). When a study was conducted by Chelliah, Khan & Atabakshi Kashi (2020), using theory of planned behaviour, the study revealed that destination image is found to be the strongest predictor in visit intention or behavioral intention of Middle Eastern medical tourists to Iran. Another study conducted by Thong, Ching & Chin (2020) showed that destination image and revisit intention is significantly related to one another. Ahmad, Ahmad & Tham (2020) used theory of planned behavior to find the relationship with the intention to stay in luxurious hotels and findings revealed that the re-intention to stay at a hotel is influenced by the positive experiential emotions of the customer. Humairah & Alversia (2021) conducted a study to examine dimensions of Halal tourism attributes and tourist experience and results show that both halal tourism attributes and travel experience positively influence destination image.

Pakistan even being geographically appealing country with favorable weather for tourism all year round, extremism has negatively affected the tourism industry and is globally recognized as a dangerous country to travel to and a study was conducted to study destination image, tourist loyalty and intention to visit the destination and data was collected from 780 tourists while the results of the study showed that destination image of Pakistan play a crucial role in attracting tourists while tourists having a pleasant trip in Pakistan is likely to recommend the destination to other tourists which affects the intention to revisit or visit (Kanwel, Linggiang, Asif, Hwang, Hussain & Jameel, 2019). Another study gave support to previous studies by contributing theoretically and empirically to destination image literature, by enhancing the understanding of the multi-dimensional aspect of destination image and its impact on revisit intention and word-of-mouth recommendation (Ragab, Mahrous & Ghoneim, 2019). A quantitative research done to examine the effect of Islamic attributes and destination image, where the data was collected from International Muslim tourists who visited Jakarta and because the Central Statistics Bureau (BPS) recorded the number of foreign visitors arriving DKI Jakarta amounted to 2,313,742 people at 2013 and, sample of 200 was employed in this study and data that was collected was analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling to test the hypotheses which revealed that the Islamic attributes and destination affective Image affect the destination Reputation while it is also revealed that destination reputation is more prominently built by destination affective image compared to Islamic attributes, while the significance of this study shown that related stakeholders that the development of destination affective image needs to be prioritized to support Jakarta's destination reputation as one of the halal tourism destinations in Indonesia (Widjaja, Khalifa & Abuelhassan, 2020). Indonesia has been a strong tourist destination globally to both Muslim and non-Muslim tourists and is still growing at a fast speed, having the growth potential to diversify or progress as an industry and with previous studies being conducted in Indonesia, it has been revealed the significance of destination image among the Muslim tourists (Siregar, Siregar, Firdaus & Muzammil, 2019).

Study conducted to learn the relationship between destination image and intention of tourist to revisit the destination mediated by service quality, tourists' satisfaction and destination trust in sharia tourism destinations in Aceh and data was collected 410 domestic and foreign tourist that come to visit Aceh while the study adopted

quantitative research method and data was analyzed using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) revealed that there is a significant relationship between destination image, and intention to visit and revisit (Siregar et al., 2019). Al-Gasawneh & Al-Adamat (2020) argued that the travel Intentions Choice and decision-making processes are at the base of behavioral and further added that , tourists form their decisions on social influence which is highly influenced by their peers, family and friends (the extent to which their peers approve of an individual making a particular choice) and their perception of the benefits that making a particular decision (to visit a destination or purchase a product and the tourist making a decision based on this is due to either positive or negative perception of the peers, family and friends on the destination along with the spouse’s perception on the destination, which ultimately aid in the tourist’s decision making process about a destination.

Researchers, emphasized on the fact that likelihood to travel to the destination or choosing the destination can be altered by the subjective norm in the theory of planned behavior where though the tourist does not have a positive perception about a destination, when a peer, family member or friend experienced the destination and confirms the destination to be positive, tourist is likely to put this into consideration and revisiting the intimal perception created in the mind of the tourist and asses weather the tourist will hold on to the previous judgement on the destination or to form an opposite judgment about the destination (Al-Gasawneh & Al-Adamat, 2020). Crompton, one of the prominent authors in destination selection process, came up with Crompton’s destination-choice model which proposed that there are two elements to the formation of a destination’s image, which are affective and cognitive components; since then, the impact of attitudes on the creation of a destination’s image have been extensively discussed in numerous studies have used theory of planned behavior to explain the relationship between destination image and tourist behavioral intention where, the perception of the peers, family and friends and the tourist’s own attitude towards the destination play a vital role in the destination choice (Al-Gasawneh & Al-Adamat, 2020). According to Crompton’s destination choice model, the destination chosen by the tourist goes through many steps in the process, before ultimately the destination is being decided and as per this model, the process begins when a tourist is aware about a destinatoon and then personal experience as well as external feedback also is factored in addition to the information gathered to a tourist on a destination (action set) and finally tourist deciding on a destination after considering all the information gathered.

Table 2: Findings

Variables	Author/s	Study	Result
Destination image, travel intention	Liu et al., (2018)	Quantitative data from 161 Muslim tourists in Taiwan	Tourist attitude also has a significant affect between destination image and travel intention. destination image positively affects tourist attitude.
Muslim consumer’s purchase behavior	Haque et.al, (2020)	Quantitative data from 110 Muslim tourists in Malaysia	Attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control positively affect Muslim consumer purchase intention towards Sharia-Complaint hotels.
Travel motivation, revisit intention and destination image	Soliman, (2019)	Quantitative data from 302 Muslim tourists in Egypt	Positive relationship between travel intention while role of attitude acts as a mediating role in attitude, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control.

Destination image and tourist loyalty	Kanwel et al., (2019)	Quantitative data from 780 Muslim tourists in Pakistan	Destination image has a significant effect on the tourist loyalty.
Destination image, revisit intention	Widjaja et al., (2020)	Quantitative data from 200 Muslim tourists in Indonesia	Destination affective image has a significant relationship to revisit intention.
Destination image, revisit intention	Siregar et al., (2019)	Quantitative data from 410 Muslim tourists in Indonesia	Destination image has a positive relationship to revisit intention.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Theory of planned behavior explains that the tourist when has a positive perception about the destination, is likely to recommend the destination to others and is behaviorally is pulled towards the destination, on the contrary, negative perception of the destination image can behaviorally pull the tourist away from the destination. From the various empirical studies, it is seen that destinations which are more Muslim-friendly or provide Muslim-friendly services, the tourists frequently travel to the destinations, in addition, tourists are likely to recommend the destination to other tourists. Several research suggest that destinations which has Muslim-friendly services is deemed by the Muslim tourists as a pleasant and welcoming destination and therefore, the destination image is positive. With this positive destination image, research provide evidence that Muslim tourists tend to not only travel often to the destination but, provide the positive perception to prospective tourists. To create a pleasant destination image to the Muslim tourists, the destination should be Muslim-friendly and the services provided should be in line with the Islamic values. According to Crescentrating 2020), Muslim tourist’s perception is directly linked with the destination’s popularity with Islamic values and how the destination was experienced by other Muslim friends, relatives, family members and spouse and hence, destinations providing services in line with Islamic values has a higher probability of creating a positive destination image for the Muslim tourist, eventually which greatly influence the behavioural intention of the Muslim tourist.

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